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**Quality Performance of Teachers: Work Environment, Work Attitude,
and Principal Supervision: Qualitative Investigation**
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Abstract:

One of the most important factors in the face of the educational system is the quality of teachers' performance. The goal of this study is to ascertain whether the teachers' high-quality performance is actually impacted by the work environment, work attitude, and principal supervision. In this qualitative investigation, the Heideggerian Phenomenology design was employed. This study seeks to comprehend the phenomenon from the participant's point of view and through their experiences. In this study, the purposive method was employed, and participants were chosen to expound on their experiences as general education teachers at PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., teaching in an inclusion classroom. It has been discovered that the key to creating a positive learning environment in the classroom is workgroup encouragement, especially having good relationships with the principal. How frequently teachers must deal with unruly and aggressive students have largely defined teaching obstacles. A teacher's perception of the supportive environment at school improved as he or she gained experience.

Keywords: Principal supervision, Teacher performance, Work attitude, Work environment

Introduction

Education, especially basic education, is the fundamental tool for human progress. It equips people to deal with life's challenges, fosters character development, strengthens one's personality, and develops one's prudence, competence, responsiveness, and intelligence (Ojiambo, 2009). Teachers, on the other hand, are vital human resources for raising educational standards. In order to generate students who are perceptive, intellectual, clever, and moral, professional teachers can plan educational activities that are successful and efficient learning. Because of this, teachers must become more competent and develop abilities in line with changing technology and professional requirements. Therefore, it is anticipated that each teacher would perform well and contribute to the achievement of both national and school-based educational objectives.

A teacher's own discipline, factors affecting the workplace, his or her professionalism, and the principal's supervision are just a few of the variables that might affect whether they perform well or poorly. An effective work ethic is one of the factors that determine a teacher's performance in the teaching and learning process. To provide a good example for their children, teachers must have a disciplined mindset. A teacher's motivation for adhering to legally mandated government laws can come from disciplinary actions. To demonstrate the professionalism of teachers, work discipline must constantly be improved. This includes arriving on time, never being late, never being absent, leaving work and returning home within the allotted time, being able to complete tasks in accordance

with goals, and using effective and efficient time management. Thus, teacher performance improves. However, the true issue is that some teachers lack discipline and break the rules, which includes showing up late for class and leaving early. Teachers frequently skip class, don't follow the regulations, and interfere with the work of the teachers. Teachers who practice proper discipline have an impact on student achievement, while teachers who practice lax discipline have an impact on student performance (Lizzio, et al., 2002).

The seamless execution of tasks in schools must be supported by efforts to increase teacher performance, which must also be supported by a work environment that is secure, cozy, and clean, with enough amenities. Both the physical (pleasant workspace, greenery/garden, and a clean building) and non-physical environments are conducive to good work (relationships between leaders and teachers and staff, and relationships between teachers and students). The distance between the teacher's room and the classroom is a physical issue, but there are also ongoing social issues between teachers that contribute to an unfriendly workplace environment. If this condition is not treated, it will have an impact on the teacher's performance since the teacher feels less at ease if he is not with his group, which causes him to leave for home more quickly and decreases motivation at work. Positive working environments influence teacher performance and heighten motivation.

The effectiveness of teachers in performing their tasks as educators is also significantly influenced by their professional attitude (Tanang & Abu, 2014). To generate students with character, teachers must act as role models for their students and be able to promote moral behavior. It is crucial for teachers to adopt a professional attitude in order to instruct and mentor their students in accordance with their roles in an effort to raise the standard and caliber of teaching. Nair and Fahimirad (2019) claimed that personality competence, pedagogical competence, social competence, and professional competence all fall under the category of teacher competency. The teacher is qualified to be referred to as a professional teacher if they possess these four qualities.

The term "principal's supervision" refers to the obligations and responsibilities of the principle as a manager to support and help subordinates in carrying out their responsibilities (Devi, et al., 2021). This supervision activity's goal is to assess the teacher's performance so that corrections can be made and student competency may be raised. It also includes coaching. In an effort to increase the caliber of learning, supervision must be done continuously (Greenberg, et al., 2011). Teachers will receive coaching under supervision to identify their weaknesses and make changes to become professional educators. The principal carries out supervision in accordance with principles and techniques because supervision carried out in accordance with procedures has a favorable influence on boosting efficiency and effectiveness in the teaching and learning process. The principal has the duty to enhance teacher performance and competency so that their performance will be better. This is crucial since the principal has a significant role in the development and success of the school. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine the quality of teachers' performance by using a qualitative investigation to assess the working environment, teachers' attitude, and principal supervision.

Review of Related Literature

Teacher Performance

Sadler (1998) stressed that performance as a teacher refers to a teacher's capacity to foster an educational learning environment for their charges. On the other hand, Danielson (2007) claimed that teacher performance refers to a teacher's proficiency in carrying out educational duties in classrooms and having obligations for students under their supervision in order to raise student accomplishment or learning outcomes. The effort put forth and the duties fulfilled by the teacher with full accountability—both in terms of quantity and quality—including the planning and execution of instructional activities, the administration of instruction, the administration of tests, and the analysis of tests—are what determine how well students perform as teachers. Teachers' internal (skills, abilities, motivation, interests, work ethic, intelligence, and ability) and external (outside influences) factors can have an impact on their performance (work environment, family, salary, communication, and facilities and infrastructure). Making lesson planning, carrying out instruction, and assessing learning results are examples of indicators that can gauge a teacher's effectiveness.

Discipline

Morgan (1980) stressed that relationship that is ordered and in which members of the organization behave in a way that is consistent with accepted organizational conduct is defined as having discipline. Behavior in terms of discipline is crucial since high marks will optimize teacher performance when carrying out their duties and are essential for academic advancement (Farrington, et al., 2012). Teachers can be guided through discipline to abide by the established regulations. Teachers can be guided through discipline to abide by the established regulations. Workplace discipline is an attitude of submission, respect, and adherence to all established norms, as well as a willingness to accept punishment when subordinates fail to do their assigned duties. Attendance, compliance with work regulations, commitment to work standards, a high degree of attention, and working ethically are all indicators of a disciplined attitude at work.

Work environment

The work environment will influence employees while they perform their jobs, which means that the work environment is any activity that has an impact on workers as they complete their assigned tasks (Reiner & Zhao, 1999). The physical work environment (lighting, air temperature, cleanliness, usage of color, security, and working hours) as well as the non-physical work environment are indicators to measure the work environment (subordinate-superior work relations & between co-workers).

Teacher's Professional Attitude

Danielson (2007) define teacher professionalism as the expertise that teachers as educators acquire to carry out their duties with full accountability and the competence to implement lesson plans and conduct evaluations. Since teaching is a profession, it is the responsibility of the teacher to balance improving competence with bettering instruction. Professional attitude, which covers the subject of a competent teacher's presence in carrying out learning accompanied by a good personality, affects teacher performance and becomes a crucial component. It is believed that there are a number of professional attitudes that every teacher has to possess, including the ability to understand theory, competency standards, and fundamental competencies, as well as the ability to develop material, professionalism, and information technology.

Principal Supervision

The supervision provided by the principal is an endeavor to raise the standard of instruction provided by teachers in accordance with strategies including planning, concrete performance, and attempts to improve student learning achievement through logical modifications (Tucker & Stronge, 2005). Murtiningsih, et al. (2019) stipulate that the term "principal supervision" refers to the service, guidance, support, and oversight provided by the principal in an effort to enhance and improve the quality of learning. The ability to supervise is a requirement for a school principal, as is the ability to perform his duties as an education supervisor, teacher coach, coach for teacher accountability, and evaluator of teaching and learning activities.

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative study employed the Heideggerian Phenomenology design. The purpose of this study is to comprehend the participant's perception of and experiences with the phenomenon better.

Sampling Technique

This study employed the purposive method, with participants chosen to discuss their experiences as general education instructors at PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., teaching in an inclusion classroom. To further narrow down the pool of potential participants for this study, an inclusion criterion was developed. 16 people in all participated in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Participants must be teachers.
2. Participants must have had classroom teaching experience in an inclusive setting.
3. The participants don't employ any one particular modality.
4. Participants are required to have at least three years of teaching experience.

Data Collection

To request his approval to conduct an interview with the chosen participants under his supervision, a transmittal letter was created and given to the school president. After receiving permission, the researchers distributed survey forms and set up interviews. The researchers employed the semi-structured interview questionnaires. This study involved twelve (12) general education teachers. The participants gave their consent for the interviews to be recorded. The researchers created a semi-structured interview guide as the test, and experts accepted and verified it. When acquiring data, the ethical guidelines outlined in this study were strictly adhered to.

Research Rigor

The researchers applied the quality criteria from Whitemore et al (2001) to ensure the study's objectivity. Further consideration of (a) Credibility and Authenticity and (b) Criticality and Integrity was given in these quality criteria. Furthermore, the researchers' use of bracketing improved the study's rigor (Cabello, 2022). Bracketing is essential for preserving impartiality and preventing biases in the conduct of the study (Alase, 2017). The participants' potential reactions were all foreseen in advance (Cabello et al., 2022). In this study, two techniques for boosting persuasiveness were used: extended periods of interaction and participant confirmation. In light of this, detailed interviews with the participants were done while upholding a comfortable setting and abiding by pertinent norms of conduct.

Ethical Consideration

This study made use of the Arifin (2018) Ethical Considerations in Qualitative Study. The following significant improvements are observed: (1) informed consent and willing cooperation; (2) anonymity and secrecy; (3) phone correspondence; (4) interview meeting; (5) information investigation and discoveries exposition; (6) moral endorsement and member access; (7) data protection; (a) interview stage; (b) cultural and linguistic barriers; and (c) handling and managing distress during the interview.

Data Analysis

In this study, the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) based on the Moustakas-popularized Modified Van Kaam Approach was employed. The data were analyzed using the responses to 10 open-ended questions on the semi-structured questionnaire during the formal interview. A coding-based, repeatable method for summarizing text utilizing smaller content categories is how the content analysis methodology is described. Consistency in terms of content analysis findings and recurring expressions is necessary in this regard; otherwise, the analysis loses its purpose and is insufficient.

Horizons	Textural Language	Themes
"A comfortable working environment can give teachers security and comfort as they perform their various obligations and the work of teaching students."	<i>physical work environment</i>	
"Based on my experience, having better ventilation like air conditioning and adequate amenities in the school increases the teaching		

<p>and learning performance of the teachers and students. I have taught in poor, average, and international class schools."</p>		
<p>"Since I've been a teacher for more than ten years, I realized how important it is to have a positive working relationship with your coworkers for both your psychological well-being and for completing your tasks and fulfilling your commitments." "A positive relationship with my coworkers lifts my spirits and motivates me to attend class in spite of the demanding workload."</p>	<p><i>psychological environment work</i></p>	<p>The environment in which teachers operate has an impact on their performance quality.</p>
<p>"I have been teaching for more than 20 years and I can really compare the attitude and behavior of students of today and students of 10 years ago. I see that students' respectfulness improves the mood and the motivation of the teachers in terms of teaching their student and in return it increases the academic achievement of the students."</p>	<p><i>non-physical work environment</i></p>	
<p>"I've been a teacher for more than 20 years, and I can certainly see a difference in the mindset and conduct of today's kids compared to those from 10 years ago. I observe that polite behavior on the part of students enhances the teachers' disposition and motivation when instructing their students, which raises the students' academic progress."</p>	<p><i>Resiliency</i></p>	
<p>"In terms of salary and other advantages, teachers in the Philippines are not as lucky as those in the nations that are close by, such Thailand, Singapore, Korea, Japan, etc. The pandemic really demonstrated how teachers need to be resilient in paving the way for better futures for their students despite challenges at work and at home."</p>	<p><i>Self-efficacy</i></p>	<p>teachers' excellent work in terms of their attitude toward their jobs</p>
<p>"Teachers need to understand that every student is different and that there is no such thing as a "one size fits all." "The teachers must have a positive outlook and believe that their students will be the nation's future good leaders and will be able to transform the current state of the country."</p>	<p><i>Optimism</i></p>	
<p>"The school principal's advice and recommendations helps us teachers strengthen our abilities and knowledge and address our areas of weakness."</p>	<p><i>Professional development</i></p>	
<p>"The sympathetic care and inspiration of the school principal positively inspire the teachers to work better in their work."</p>	<p><i>Motivation</i></p>	<p>The effect of principal supervision on teachers' performance quality</p>

Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed three emerging themes:

Theme 1: The environment in which teachers operate has an impact on their performance quality.

Theme 2: Teachers' excellent work in terms of their attitude toward their jobs

Theme 3: The effect of principal supervision on teachers' performance quality

Theme 1: The environment in which teachers operate has an impact on their performance quality.

The level of participation and production throughout school organizations is significantly influenced by job satisfaction. The level of job satisfaction among teachers has a big impact on how committed they are to the whole school. According to T2, "Teachers who are content with their employment will also devote themselves to the work in the organization." This suggests that the more engaged and committed employees are to the organization, the more satisfied they are with their jobs. The success of the school as a whole is influenced by the general working environment and the happiness of the teachers with their workplace.

Through the mediation of work-life quality, high-performance work systems have a direct and indirect impact on teachers' in-role performance and extracurricular behavior. The relationship between high-performance work systems and employee work behavior depends in large part on the quality of the employee experience at work. The association between job engagement and work performance is statistically significant, and teachers' self-efficacy has a favorable influence on both. In workforce education institutions, the mediating effects of self-efficacy and job engagement on the association between corporate cultures that value learning and teacher job performance were also noted.

Regardless of the school's student population, according to T6, "the work environment for teachers is incredibly essential to us, and ultimately to our students; teachers are happier and plan to remain longer in schools with positive work environments." The most crucial factors in raising teachers' performance standards are not having pristine facilities or access to cutting-edge instructional technologies. It also includes task structure, such as workload and supervision, cultural and social variables, as well as the strength and quality of the staff and students. The physical environment, such as safety and comfort, and economic variables, such as compensation and job security, are important aspects of hiring teachers.

Unsurprisingly, people who want to enhance teachers' working conditions in order to enhance student learning frequently concentrate on easily modifiable elements like pay, class size, and job security. Many components of the teaching profession, however, continue to fall outside the scope of policy formulation, legal control, and dispute resolution. These aspects of the social backdrop of education have a significant impact on initiatives to enhance educational institutions and students' academic achievement. Regardless of variables like mood and subjective well-being, perceptions of how they are appreciated at work and at home, as well as how effectively they manage a balance between their personal and professional lives, are all connected to the school's executive training.

"Teachers are a crucial part of the teaching process," declared T9. Additionally, T1 stated that "Unity among members will have a major impact as it will manifest responsibility in all of the teacher's actions," so in this regard, school leaders need to make sure that teachers who perform well in their schools receive due recognition to boost their self-esteem and make them feel safe. In order to help teachers increase their self-efficacy and eventually the quality of their instruction, professional development must be ensured.

By starting initiatives to involve parents and community people, attending seminars, workshops, and current conferences, teachers were able to carry out their work in the teaching process very successfully, according to the teachers' overall performance. However, teachers monitor and evaluate students' development extremely well or outstandingly well, and they encourage slow learners outside of class as well.

Teachers' perceptions of the world have an impact on how they feel, think, and act. The Encouragement Task Force addressed teachers' perceptions of maintaining a positive relationship with school leaders and teachers will be encouraged to use their skills or initiative to teach, having opportunities to express ideas or opinions, receiving regular positive feedback, and feeling valued for their role. According to T3, encouraging work groups is the most important factor in maintaining a positive learning environment.

On the other hand, in decisions about curriculum reform and staff consultation, organizational encouragement was viewed as being less significant than supervisory encouragement, particularly the requirement for assistance and training. Physical facilities are the least significant factor or component that addresses organizational encouragement, and the most significant aspect or component is promoting positive behavior at work through avoiding conflict in order to maintain fairness. The challenges teachers encounter—also referred to as teaching barriers—depend on how frequently they deal with disruptive and aggressive children. Overbearing parents, poor or gloomy recreation facilities, or other issues are unimportant to the teachers. Too many after-school meetings, unreasonable deadlines, and office staff checks, according to teachers, all contribute to the stress of their jobs.

There is no doubt that views of the workplace varied from one teacher to the next and from one teacher level to another; however, we should keep in mind that not all organizations, even those in the same industry and line of business, are the same in terms of structure, culture, vision, mission, etc. No individual has the same character, attitude, and personality.

Theme 2: Teachers' excellent work in terms of their attitude toward their jobs

Even before the pandemic, the job of a teacher in the Philippines was extremely emotionally taxing, especially for those who were assigned to remote mountainous areas. Teachers who are assigned in the mountain areas tend to stay there for a week due to the geographic location such as you need to travel by boat, by horse, and even crossing the river which is very dangerous when during training and typhoon. "Teaching in hazardous community is not really easy imagine that you need to travel more than 5 hours just to get to the school and all the means of transportation are through horseback riding."

The amount of teachers' work-related stress has significantly increased throughout the epidemic, particularly in terms of paper-work deadlines. T3 said, "It seems that in the department of education it is now a matter of hypocrisy, almost everything is not genuine even the reports needed to submit in the regional office." Some teachers confess that they even leave their classes just to finish the overload paper works that need to submit urgently. T7 said, "If the aim of the department of education is to provide quality education they must first lessen the teacher's paperworks." Due to an abundance of paperwork, there have been many more complaints of teachers suffering from melancholy, stress, and anxiety throughout the pandemic.

Despite the challenges and problems we have faced, resilience helps the instructor remain productive, according to T11. Therefore, through initial training, ongoing professional development, and support networks, teachers' resilience can be fostered at all career stages. Most importantly, school leadership may make a significant contribution to the growth of both individual and group resilience. Resilience is a capacity that develops through interactions between people in organizational environments, not just a personal quality.

Even if technology has advanced more recently, there is always a constant need for teachers who are professional development. It is believed that one of the keys to raising kids' academic achievement is teachers' self-efficacy. Teacher efficacy is claimed to be a significant factor in teacher effectiveness and to be reliably correlated with both teacher actions and student results. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that schools with high performance professional development incorporate crucial facets that foster and encourage the growth of abilities and self-efficacy beliefs. This study makes the argument that self-efficacy should be a conceptually sound focus of training designs targeted at improving teacher competency and, by extension, improving student outcomes, in the framework of professional development for teachers. Teachers can boost student outcomes and deepen the significance of teaching and learning experiences by actively participating in professional development opportunities including webinars, seminars, free certifications, and service projects, according to T12. A practical and promising method for achieving this goal is to use teacher self-efficacy as the organizing principle around which teacher in-service training can be developed and assessed.

Teaching is not simple; it is complex and dynamic when taking into account the diversity of students in the classroom, according to T7. "Teaching is not static by nature; as the world changes, so do the teaching strategies and approaches." In order to meet the competencies set forth by the department of education, teachers must be effective. This depends on how they use pedagogical strategies and how they encourage and inspire their students. There is little doubt that teachers have an impact on students' academic performance and achievement. One of the key elements influencing pupils' progress is the teacher's optimism, according to research. Improvement in trust positively affects the relationship of students and teachers by this relationship it creates a culture will the teacher prepare the environment for the student development, as stated in T4: "Teacher optimism towards students creates trust and this trust creates better interaction between the teacher and the students and because of this it helps the students to be guided on its studies as well as its difficulties encountered in life."

Theme 3: The effect of principal supervision on teachers' performance quality

A school's principal is a manager with significant administrative and managerial responsibilities. To lead and guide others toward a common objective is both an art and a science. Leadership also entails having the essential knowledge and abilities to carry out duties and responsibilities. We underestimate how complex leadership is; it has a wide range of meanings in social, political, cultural, and educational contexts.

The DepEd Memorandum No. 050, s. 2020, was issued by the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) aims to strengthen and develop the leadership skills of school leaders. Institutions have benefited from the different seminars, programs, and courses that the government and other departments have developed. In times of opportunity and crisis, developing leaders is said to benefit the country by improving management effectiveness and efficiency.

"The principal's oversight of the instructors, particularly when it comes to enhancing experience and knowledge, has a positive impact on the teachers", according to T4. One of the constant and most important responsibilities of the principal, the leader in the teaching-learning environment, is supervision. It must be mentioned that the

principal must correct the teacher in a constructive manner and must make sure that the teacher never feels inferior. The principal sets clear objectives and points the group in the right path. It is impossible to ignore his duties as a supervisory leader. According to Nwogo (2012), supervisory leadership guides, comforts, counsels, and helps achieve the desired learning outcomes. According to Tayebwa, et al. (2021), instructional supervision is crucial for ensuring the qualitative and quantitative quality of teachers' and students' performance. When guiding the teaching-learning process, the principle must be skilled in both theory and practice. Supervisory leadership promotes growth on both a personal and professional level and cares about maximizing the potential of both faculty and students.

The persuasive voice of the leader should never be undervalued; it consistently has a positive effect on the caliber and success of the endeavor. As T11 stated, "Principal who carried his or her task sincerely and with empathetic heart have increased the productivity of the teachers and it encourages them to practice effective activities that could lead to quality teaching and learning performance." A leader's capacity to inspire a sizable group of men and persuade them to complete the task and purpose to the very end is considered as a key and imperative capability. Because it can affect dedication, empowerment, involvement, cooperation, and total bodily performance, an influential voice is crucial.

The major supervising leadership was a reflection of the caliber of the performance of the instructors and students. For the improvement of the teacher-student learning process, the harmonious operation of the institution, and efficient classroom control and environment, his comprehension, monitoring, analysis, and evaluation abilities are essential. A strong leader with broad management and leadership expertise should be the principal. He must uphold the standards, create a warm, secure environment that is engaging, and ensure that the learning process is of the highest caliber.

Conclusion

What steps may be taken to guarantee that every classroom has a competent instructor? It is clear that understanding how teachers perceive their working environments is crucial for improving educational environments. Because some aspects of the workplace are seen negatively, this could have a negative impact on well-being. The presence of persistent emotional and interpersonal stressors that create burnout in the workplace is not a good signal for the quality performance of the teachers.

On the other hand, it is evident that improvements in attitudes, motivation, and a positive organizational culture in schools can increase teacher performance. Through the mediation of work-life quality, high-performance work systems have a direct and indirect impact on teachers' in-role performance and extracurricular behavior. The relationship between high-performance work systems and employee work behavior depends in large part on the quality of the employee experience at work.

Furthermore, it is the primary duty of school administrators to support the effective delivery of instruction. To ensure that teachers are adequately prepared to raise student performance, effective school leaders regularly involve them in classroom discussions and reflection activities. A multitude of instructional approaches that either directly or indirectly support teacher professional development are known to effective school leaders.

More specifically, the study shows that school administrators, the teacher's attitude toward his or her job, and the work environment all play critical roles in the development of "professional communities" of teachers who support one another in order to improve teaching. This is significant since studies have linked professional communities to strong student performance on standardized math examinations. The researchers conclude that when school administrators and teachers collaborate, teacher-teacher working relationships are strengthened and student achievement increases.

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